

Development of Corruption and Impact on Education

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Abstract: Measures to prevent corruption, one of the negative vices of society in our country, as well as the development, history, and definitions of corruption, and its impact on education are studied.

Keywords: corruption, education system, globalization, management, higher education.

A number of scientific centers, international organizations, major scientists, public and political figures are conducting practical and fundamental research on the prevention of corruption in world science.

In particular, research on the aspects of determining the causes of corruption, its structural structure, their description, and classification is gaining importance. At the same time, the population is creating the need for a new socio-philosophical research of the fundamental foundations of the positive tendencies of young people in the formation and development of the consciousness of fighting against corruption and the indicators of the socio-political, spiritual and educational aspects of its implementation.

One of the main priorities of the state policy is the implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at preventing corruption, one of the negative vices of society's life in our country. From this point of view, socio-philosophical research of the modern conceptual foundations of the improvement of the mechanisms, criteria and laws of forming and improving the culture of fighting against corruption of the population remains an important research object of the scientific community.

In the issue of defining the concept of "corruption", a number of significant studies were conducted by scientists in the CIS countries, in which the following definitions were given to the concept of "corruption". For example, V.V. Luneev defines corruption as "...a socio-legal or criminological phenomenon that covers a set of socially dangerous actions that are criminalized and (for various reasons) not criminalized, but recognized as criminal in world practice"¹

A.V. Kuzmin says "two concepts of corruption, i.e., first, a broad concept that includes bribery and violation of official powers in all branches of government and management (state, municipal, private); secondly, a narrow understanding of corruption is a certain level of incitement that is conditionally committed in all types of activities that involve bribery. Both types of corruption ruthlessly destroy the legal foundations of society and state power", I.D. Fialkovskaya: "Corruption is a socially dangerous illegal phenomenon, which is the selfish use of public officials' powers for personal or other interests, as well as the official powers associated with them. is to use with"², – деган таърифларни беришган.

If we analyze all of these definitions, it mainly focuses on two aspects of the issue, firstly, the abuse of the position held by any person or organized groups for the purpose of obtaining some material

¹ Luneev V.V. Коррупция: политические, экономические, организационные и правовые проблемы (Тезисы доклада) // Государство и право. 2000. № 4. – С.101.

² Фиалковская И.Д. Коррупция: понятие, признаки, виды.// Вестник Нижегородского университета им. Н.И. Лобачевского, 2018, №1 С. 137-142.

benefit; on the other hand, an attempt was made to define it as a type of crime resulting from the guilty actions of officials.

Corruption, first of all, leads to the violation and humiliation of a person's dignity, honor, dignity, mainly political, economic and social rights. One of the goals and important tasks of the fight against corruption with enlightenment is to build strong confidence in the minds of the population that justice will be done today and in the future, to ensure the rule of law and to take prompt measures to prevent human rights violations. .

A survey was conducted in order to study the opinions and opinions of young people who are just entering higher education. All categories of respondents participating in this study emphasized the need to research higher education, including access to higher education institutions, and relationships between participants in the educational process in higher education institutions. The participants believe that there is not enough transparency in the higher education system, especially in the matter of admission to OTM. Almost 700 parents, 346 teachers and 20 principals offered to study the dangers of corruption in the higher education system. Some of the parents in Tashkent offered to study the reasons why pedagogical graduates do not want to work in their specialties.

It was also mentioned that it is necessary to increase the number of practical trainings for future teachers and to improve the quality of teaching in universities. In informal corruption, a secret or information known to members of a certain society or group (insiders) is unknown to people outside it (outsiders). Nowadays, it can be said that this type of corruption has somewhat changed its form and adapted to the requirements of the times. Targeted admissions corruption, a less visible type of corruption in higher education, is dangerous. In Russia, this type of corruption is widespread and regularly committed by public servants. In this case, civil servants use targeted admission to enroll the children of their relatives or acquaintances.

Since 2017, the admission of applicants to study on the basis of targeted admission has also started in Uzbekistan. Corruption can also be encountered in the development of a targeted admissions program. Because many officials try to get their relatives into higher education institutions through these programs. In such cases, they use informal corruption. In the United States of America and the Russian Federation, during the last century, officials (gatekeepers) enrolled their loved ones in this way. It is clear from this that it is necessary to carefully consider the applicants entering the targeted admission. Along with the educational process, corruption has penetrated deeply into the management process of higher education. For example, we can see this in the proper use of the funds allocated for the material and technical base of the university, in the setting of bonuses for teachers, and in the accreditation of universities.

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